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Do authorship regulations in performance-based funding systems affect authorship practices? A case study of German medical faculties

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Introduction

The implementation of performance-based funding systems (PBFS) at German universities started in the early 1990's. Medical faculties in the new federal states were encouraged to allocate funding in a performance-based manner to quickly catch up with the faculties of the old federal states (Brähler & Strauß, 2009). However, a major reason for the introduction of PBFS was that faculties tried to distribute their increasingly scarce money resources as much as possible according to objective criteria (*ibid*). There are PBFS on the federal state level and on the institutional level, whereby individual departments and clinics of a medical faculty compete for funding. The criteria for the allocation of funds vary among medical faculties but mostly include the raising of third-party funds and the quantity and “quality” of publication output that largely relies on the journal impact factors (JIF). Whereas some faculties consider only publications listed in PubMed, other faculties take publication venues such as books or proceedings into account. The attribution of JIF scores to authors differs widely among faculties. There is either no distinction of author positions (whole counting) so that the JIF of the publication venue equals the final JIF score, or authorship regulations rate every author position differently and even take joint first and last authorships into account.

The German Research Foundation (DFG) has repeatedly criticized the use of PBF in medicine making numerous suggestions such as the memorandum on the application of PBF at medical faculties (DFG, 2004). The DFG recommended to calculate the PBF of a unit (department or clinic) by considering the unweighted JIF of publications and to rate first and last authorship with one third each. The remaining third should be split among all middle authors to prevent additional benefits from increasing the number of authors. The results of the third-party funding calculation (sums) and the publication success (JIF sum) should be considered in a ratio of 1:1 (*ibid*). Most German medical faculties perceived the DFG model as normative (Brähler & Strauß, 2009) and still apply a pure JIF-based model.

As only a few medical faculties provide public information on their PBFS, a survey was conducted to find out which medical faculties adapted the authorship regulation proposed by the DFG and which faculties implemented their own authorship regulation. There is no evidence yet on whether the DFG recommendation has affected the authorship practices of German medical scientists. The purpose of this study is thus to empirically explore if and in how far

authorship regulations may have influenced the author count and author position of medical research publications.

Theoretical considerations on authorship in medicine

The number of authors per paper is rising across all scientific fields due to the increasing pressure to publish, wider collaborative efforts, and a trend towards team-based research (Lapidow & Scudder, 2019). Hence, authorship can become a contentious issue in collaborative publishing and disputes often arise concerning authorship attribution or order (Resnik et al., 2020). In medicine, authorship order is based on the relevance and type of the contribution and the hierarchical position within the research team (Mongeon et al., 2017). Generally, the first author conducted the majority of the work and is mostly a postdoctoral fellow or a doctoral student as first-authored papers are often required for graduation (Burrows & Moore, 2011). In regard to last authorship, Gaeta (1999) reported that many scientists reserve the last position for the senior member of the research group or the department director who has a supervisory function. Similarly, Costas & Bordons (2011) found that the last author position is reserved for persons who contributed least to the work but are renowned, which encourages honorary or gift authorship. According to Tschardt et al. (2007) last authors often get as much credit as first authors, because they are assumed to be the driving force behind the research – financially and intellectually. Thus, although there is agreement that first authors have the greatest responsibility, there is no such agreement about last-listed authors (Burrows & Moore, 2011). In the absence of author bylines or author contribution statements, it is difficult to determine if the last position denotes a major contribution or rather a minor one (Cleary et al., 2012).

Unlike first and last authorship, the position of the middle author is less straightforward. Middle authors are either in order of their relative contribution to the work or in alphabetical order. While it is often assumed that middle authors have contributed less than first and last authors they may have indeed contributed more than the last author. However, it is also common practice in medicine to list all participating scientists as (middle) authors, even if someone has only provided data for a clinical study.

Authorship in medicine is a delicate topic and the inflation of author counts raises questions relating to authorship practices. Increasing author counts may not necessarily reflect a growth in collaboration, but rather the rewarding of small contributions with authorship (Mongeon et al., 2017), especially if scientists define authorship loosely to obtain an advantage over scientists who adhere to recommended authorship criteria (Baethge, 2008). Thus, fair authorship regulations could prevent the unjustified inflation of co-authors.

Database and Methods

To expand on the limited available data on PBFS at German medical faculties, a systematic analysis and survey was conducted among all 37 medical faculties in Germany to request information on authorship regulations and publication criteria. The bibliometric data used in this study are sourced from the German Competence Centre of Bibliometrics' in-house version of the Web of Science (WoS). The analysis focuses on medical publications of German universities. The identification of universities relies on the institutional coding that exists for all German institutions and is regularly updated (Winterhager et al., 2014). However, it is not yet possible to delineate the publication output of universities' medical faculties. To capture the medical publications of a university, the OECD Fields of Science and Technology (FOS) classification was used, which has been concorded from WoS' Subject Categories classification scheme. Articles and reviews published in journals and assigned to the OECD field "Medical and Health Sciences" are analysed in this study. Publications are examined for the period 2009

to 2020, because the quality of the data linking authors with affiliations prior to 2008 in WoS is inadequate. There are two methods for counting publications with more than one author – whole counting or fractional counting. Whole counting assigns a whole count of the paper to each author. Thus, one paper is considered as one contribution from each author and the department with which they are affiliated. Evidently, this method of counting inflates the overall number of publications. One method of remedying this inflation is to use fractional counting, whereby each author is awarded a proportion of the paper and the total number of publications remains at one. Fractional counting was conducted at the level of the author and aggregated to the medical-faculty level. The author count and author position in WoS was used to determine the fractional count of one publication. To remedy the increase of author counts per publication, publications were limited to those with an author count less than 100.

Results

The results section starts with an overview of authorship regulations practiced at medical faculties of German state universities (Table 1). It is notable that 10 out of 37 medical faculties strictly apply the DFG recommendation. There are also 10 medical faculties that attribute authorship credit based on whole counting. Moreover, 6 faculties have adapted the DFG recommendation for authorship weighting with varying percentages that are attributed to first and last authors. Interestingly, there are 4 medical faculties that apply whole counting to first and last authors only. Two of the medical faculties have no PBFS, one of which is a young faculty that aims at introducing PBF in the following years and the other faculty uses performance-based indicators as a gratification system.

Table 1. Overview of authorship regulations among all 37 German medical faculties.

Authorship regulation	Number of medical faculties
DFG recommendation (1/3 first author, 1/3 last author, 1/3 middle authors)	10
Whole counting of authorship (irrespective of author position)	10
Adaptation of DFG recommendation (variant attribution of authorship credit)	6
Attribution of whole counting to first and last author only	4
no PBFS	2
<i>unknown</i>	5
Total number of German medical faculties	37

The following analyses focus on the publication data of the 10 medical faculties with DFG recommendation and those 10 faculties with whole-counting systems. All of these faculties have a distribution-based PBFS where departments and clinics compete for funding. Figure 1 provides an overview of the average author count per paper according to authorship regulation. It is striking that the average number of authors per paper has steadily grown in the period 2009 to 2020. However, it might be noted that the average number of authors is higher in the group of publications with a whole-counting authorship system than in the group of publications with the DFG authorship regulation. This aligns with the DFG recommendation to counteract the increasing number of authors by a more prudent handling of authorship.

Figure 1. Average number of authors per publication according to authorship regulation.

Figure 2 visualizes the average institution count (left panel) and the average country count (right panel) per paper. It shows that the average number of institutions per paper has nearly doubled over the last 12 years. The lower author count of authors publishing with the DFG regulation at their faculty coincides with a lower institution count as these scientists may be more careful in defining authorship. Interestingly, the average number of institutions converges in the two distinct publication sets. Similarly, the average number of countries has increased over the years and is higher in the set of publications that are fully attributed.

Figure 2. Average number of institutions (left panel) and countries (right panel) per paper according to authorship regulation.

To provide findings on the author position according to authorship regulation, I examine in Figure 3 the share of first-authored publications over time, the share of last-authored publications over time, the share of purely middle-authored publications over time and the share of publications with both first- and last authorship over time.

Figure 3. Overview of the share of publications according to authorship regulation and author position.

The figures reveal that the share of first or last authorship papers decreased over the last years at the expense of a rising share of middle-authorship papers, irrespective of authorship regulation. It is evident that the share of publications in first or last authorship is higher in the group of publications with DFG recommendation. A possible explanation could be that scientists internalized the DFG authorship regulation and make an effort to be first or last author when publishing. Another indication is that the share of middle-authorship papers is lower than in the set of publications which are fully attributed. These obvious trends raise the question of comparability of these two publication sets. Hence, Figure 4 presents the overall publication output according to authorship regulation.

Figure 4. Publication output according to authorship regulation.

It is striking that the numbers of publications have similarly grown over the 12 years. The sharp rise in 2020 in publications is COVID-related. To rule out that the differing author counts and author position shares are not an artifact of the medical focus of faculties, Figure 5 presents the share of publications according to WoS' subject categories. The top 15 subject categories are listed in descending order. The majority of publications have their origin in neurosciences, followed by oncology and clinical neurology. The differences in shares are overall minor and concern only a few fields such as clinical neurology, radiology, or psychiatry.

Figure 5. Overview of main WoS Subject Categories according to authorship regulation.

Finally, as most PBFS consider JIF scores for the allocation of funds, it is of interest to find out in how far the average JIF of publications differs according to authorship regulation.

Figure 6. Average JIF of publications according to authorship regulation.

At first glance, Figure 6 suggests that the average JIF per publication has increased rapidly over the period 2009-2018. Moreover, the figure reveals that scientists at faculties with whole

counting of authorship publish on average in journals with a higher JIF in comparison to scientists affiliated with medical faculties at which the DFG recommendation applies.

Discussion

The research question guiding this study was whether authorship regulations have an impact on the authorship position and author count in medical publications. In the first instance, results indicate a significant increase in the author numbers per publication, irrespective of authorship regulation. Similarly, the number of institutions and countries has steadily grown over the last years. In terms of author positions, the results show that in the set of publications where the DFG authorship regulation applies, the share of publications in first or last authorship is higher than in the set of publications with whole counting. This could be an indication of the incentive role the authorship regulation plays by rewarding the first and last author more than the middle author.

Most PBFS rely on JIF scores and are thus affected by authorship constellations and name order. Following the DFG recommendation, the contribution of middle authors to PBF yields low JIF scores. Results show that the share of middle authors is lower in the set of publications where the DFG recommendation applies compared to the set with whole counting. One benefit of the DFG recommendation is that scientists might be more eager to be first or last author because these author positions are higher rated. One evident drawback of the DFG authorship regulation is that it might discourage collaboration and unjustly divides the credit due to the predefined shares assigned to author positions. Moreover, this counting can disadvantage departments that regularly collaborate as they lose a proportion of these papers from their totals.

In contrast, whole-counting is intuitive and requires no administrative effort to keep track of author positions. Interestingly, the average JIF of publications is higher in the set of publications which are fully attributed. The question arises why the administrative burden of taking author positions into account should be maintained, especially if the full attribution of authorship seems to correlate with a higher citation impact? One evident drawback of whole counting is that collective authorships are treated equally. Moreover, whole counting may lead to author inflation and encourages unethical publication practices such as gift authorship where authors are named although they did not contribute. However, it cannot be ruled out that the DFG authorship regulation likewise fosters unethical authorship practices.

Furthermore, the replies of the survey showed that some medical faculties with whole counting deliberately refrain from fractional counting because they do not want to interfere in the publishing practice of medical scientists and are thus unperturbed by the trend towards increased author counts. On the contrary, some medical faculties, which have currently a whole-counting authorship regulation intend to introduce data collection systems that allow the distinction of author positions. Other German medical faculties adapted the DFG recommendation by introducing additional regulations in order not to punish large collaborations with a small share of reward. In contrast, they reward the added value of networking and collaboration with a higher attribution of JIF scores to middle authors.

Conclusion

In light of a fair allocation of funds, it is important to better understand how authorship regulations may influence the outcomes of performance-based indicators. This study has shown in how far the authorship regulation proposed by the DFG in 2004 might have affected the author count and author position of medical publications. The DFG authorship regulation was intended to counteract the trend towards increasing author numbers in medical publications.

The results indicate a general trend of increased author counts and middle authorship papers. However, the publications with the DFG authorship regulation have lower author counts and lower shares of middle-authorship papers.

Even though the results may be affected by a number of other criteria, this study provides some useful, preliminary results to this issue and suggests some areas for further investigation. A fair distribution of authorship credit remains important and could suppress the tendency to unjustified inflation of co-authors because authors will be more reluctant to share their authorship with peers not truly involved in the publication (Vavryčuk, 2018). So far, bibliometric databases only include author positions and author counts. One challenge is the identification of joint first and last authorships because the byline is not included in bibliometric databases. A more complete provision of data on author contribution statements, would allow for more accurate indicators that take author position and contribution into account.

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